

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF POTENTIAL THERAPEUTIC APPROACH FOR CORRECTION OF DERMATITIS OF DIFFERENT NATURE

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Abstract

Introduction. The Klotho gene contributes to the suppression of age-related changes and has anti-inflammatory effects induced by overexpression. Therefore, it could be used as an alternative approach to prevent and treat atopic dermatitis (AD) at the molecular level.

Current therapeutic approaches focusing on superficial treatment of affected skin areas are not fully effective. In the present study, we have developed a novel approach that will potentially reverse apoptosis and prevent AD using exosomes overexpressing Klotho.

The aim of this study- is to develop a targeted delivery method for correction of skin barrier disorders using an adapted algorithm to recruit additional copies of the Klotho gene into target cells and a method to validate its overexpression.

Materials and methods. A methodology was staged to induce overexpression of Klotho gene by adapting a previously developed technology of PCR product ligation into an empty vector and transforming cell lines by incorporating a plasmid with ligated PCR product into bacterial cells (E.Coli.).

Results and discussion. The present work has resulted in a well-established algorithm for the production, generation and targeting of potential therapeutic agent, Klotho gene, by using exosomes. The overexpression of the Klotho gene was assessed by real-time PCR. This algorithm can be applied to both naturally and artificially induced overexpression of the Klotho gene. Exosomes carrying the beneficial gene will allow for therapeutic effects at different stages of AD. This methodology is versatile and can be implemented according to the needs of a particular laboratory.

Conclusions. In conclusion, exosomal therapy with Klotho is a potential therapeutic agent for clinical interventions for dermatitis of different genesis.

Keywords: Klotho gene, expression, transfection, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), exosomes, inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is an inflammatory skin disorder affecting up to 20% of the paediatric population worldwide. Patients with AD usually have dry and itchy skin and are at increased risk of developing asthma and allergic rhinitis. AD is known to have a strong genetic component with a presumed heritability of over 60% [1]. Variants of loss of filaggrin function are the most observed genetic risk factor among more than 40 genes associated with a predisposition to AD [1,2]. The function of the human genome is altered over the course of life by external factors. At the same time, external factors change gene expression without affecting the information contained in them - epigenetic rearrangements [2, 3].

The skin barrier function is provided by keratinocytes of the upper epidermis layer and the water-lipid mantle covering its surface. Normally, keratinocytes

are bound together by desmosomes, ensuring the integrity of the epidermis and protecting the underlying layers from drying out. Due to high content of lipids in epidermis, fat-soluble substances can penetrate it, while it is practically impermeable to water and aqueous solutions. The water-lipid mantle is acidic, which weakens or neutralises the effect of many aggressive factors and prevents pathogens from entering the skin. Damage to the lipid structure of the stratum corneum and thinning of the water-lipid film - the main skin defect in atopic dermatitis causing increased permeability to allergens and irritants can be caused by genetic factors, among others.

This has prompted further investigation into the pathogenesis of the disease and the development of a new targeted approach to the correction and prevention of AD through the use of a secreted form of Klotho.

We aim to confirm the hypothesis that Klotho has a beneficial effect on dermatitis of various genesis by reducing apoptosis and inflammation [3-6].

Exosomes are small membrane vesicles formed by the fusion of multi vesicular lysosomes with plasma membranes and extracellular release of intraluminal vesicles [4, 5]. Exosomes released from mesenchymal multipotent stromal stem cells (MSCs) show anti-inflammatory and can repair skin damage.

AD is based on genetic and epigenetic changes that can be corrected and prevented.

Therefore, the use of exosomes for Klotho secretion could be a potential anti-inflammatory agent in AD therapy.

The aim of this study was to develop a method for targeted delivery of a useful gene to correct skin barrier disorders using an adapted algorithm to recruit additional copies of the Klotho gene into target cells and a method to validate hyper expression

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Exosomes production

The aim of this study is to improve the treatment of skin lesions. The objective is achieved by changing the general pattern of application of cellular material - using exosomes secreted by these cells instead of whole cells. Exosomes are important mediators of physiological intercellular communication. The physiology of exosomal transport offers the possibility of targeted drug delivery to the target cells, which allows a new mode of therapy in many therapeutic areas. The latter can be implemented through the ability of exosomes to incorporate a biologically active payload into their internal content through the overexpression of genes responsible for the synthesis of necessary substances in the producing cell. Thus, to increase their regenerative potential, human fibroblasts are transfected with genetic plasmid vectors providing ectopic expression of Klotho secreted genes (Addgene plasmid 17713) during cultivation. Primary cell culture is obtained from a patient's biopsy specimen taken under local anesthesia from the patient's own buttock area.

Genetic constructs

Plasmids were isolated from a transgenic E.coli line using the MiniprepKit commercial kit (D4015, ZymoResearch, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. For this purpose, 5 ml of bacterial culture grown in liquid LB medium (SigmaAldrich, USA) supplemented with the selective antibiotic ampicillin 75 µg/ml (SigmaAldrich, USA) was centrifuged at 200 g for 10 min. The precipitate was resuspended in buffer. The bacteria were then lysed in the buffer and centrifuged at 15000 g for 3 minutes. Plasmid DNA was isolated from the supernatant using columns and purified with washing buffer from MiniprepKit.

Quantitative and qualitative analysis of plasmid DNA and assessment of expression levels

The isolated plasmid DNA was diluted in wash buffer (Miniprep). Quantitative counts were performed on a spectrophotometer (BIO-RAD) at 260 nm. Qualitative analysis was performed at 280 nm followed by evaluation of A260/A280 ratio. The samples were considered suitable at A260/A280 = 1.8±0.05. The copy number of the obtained plasmid DNA solutions was

calculated using the formula: (amount of DNA (ng)*6.022x10²³) / (plasmid length (bp)*1x10⁹*650). For subsequent PCR in qualitative and quantitative formats, a series of dilutions with known copy number in 1 µl solution were prepared: 3*10⁵, 3*10⁴, 3*10³.

PCR identification of a useful gene

For the identification of the nucleotide sequence of isolated plasmids primers to the sites lying within the first two exons of Klotho gene were used: KL (forward), CACAACCTCCTCCTGGCTCAT and KL (reverse), TCCAGTGGAGCTTAGGCA. The following thermocycling parameters were used: 95 °C for 2 min followed by 35 cycles: 95 °C for 15 s, 62 °C for 15 s and a final elongation at 72 °C for 7 min.

PAGE electrophoresis, excision and elution of PCR products

The PCR products obtained from the reaction were separated in a 6% polyacrylamide gel (BIO-RAD) using a vertical electrophoresis chamber (BIO-RAD) at 150 V constant voltage for 45 min. The fragment length marker used was a low-stranded DNA molecular ruler (Fermentas) stained with 1% ethidium bromide and visualized under UV-radiation. The specificity of the reaction was assessed by the absence of fragments of length other than 103 bp. The fragments were cut out using a scalpel and placed in 40 µl ddH₂O for 24 hours to allow elution of the product from the gel.

Sequencing

Sanger sequencing was performed to verify the results obtained. Sequence analysis and alignment were performed using SequencingAnalysis software (AppliedBiosystems). The obtained consensus sequences were compared with reference sequences using the BLAST database (ncbi).

Cell culture and transfection

The MMSCs were cultured in DulbeccoF-12(Sigma) medium containing 20% fetal bovine serum in an incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂. The cells, upon reaching the logarithmic growth phase (8 × 10⁵ cells/ml), were transfected by Escort III (SigmaAldrich, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA-lipid complexes were added to the pre-prepared cell cultures, incubated for 16 h and the medium was changed to standard growth medium.

RNA isolation and reverse transcription

Transfected cultures were washed three times with PBS solution and removed from matrices. Total RNA was isolated using TrizolTriReagent (Sigma) according to the manufacturer's instructions. RNA isolates were then converted to cDNA using a reverse transcription reagent kit (Fermentas, USA).cDNA was amplified using a SYBR Green PCR kit (Thermo, USA). The Roche- Lightcycler Real-Time PCR detection system was used to record the amplification product. The primer sequences were as follows: Klotho (forward: 5' TCCCTCTTTTACCTGAGAAC 3'; reverse: 5' CGGATGGCAGAGAGAGAAATCAAC 3') and GAPDH (forward: 5' GGAGTCTACTGGCGTCTTCAC 3'; reverse: 5' ATGAGCCCTTCCACGATGC 3').

Results. A cell culture was obtained hyperexpressing the Klotho gene. Vesicles secreted by these cells contained a large number of proteins of Klotho

family. The increase of gene expression was registered by Real-time PCR method. The expression of the Klotho gene was assessed by the number of copies of informational RNA compared to the number of copies of the housekeeping gene GAPDH. In the control group, the number of klotho RNA copies was about 25 times higher than the number of copies of the GAPDH gene.

Conclusions:

1) An algorithm for targeting delivery of a beneficial gene into target cells using the Klotho gene as an example has been developed.

2) The cytoplasmic origin of exosomes can be complemented with biologically active molecules and genes to correct the epigenetic landscape of cells.

3) The protocol developed provides promise for the use of exosomes as a means of delivering bioactive substances to target cells and can be adapted to the application of other beneficial genes.

References

1. Watson W., Kapur S. (2021) Atopic dermatitis. *Allergy. Asthma. Clin. Immunol*; 7 (Suppl. 1): S4. doi: 10.1186/1710-1492-7-S1-S4.
2. Hu MC, Shi M, Zhang J, et al. (2010) Klotho: a novel phosphaturic substance acting as an autocrine enzyme in the renal proximal tubule. *FASEB J.* 24:3438–3450.
3. Kurosu H, Yamamoto M, Clark JD, et al. (2005). Suppression of aging in mice by the hormone Klotho. *Science*309:1829–1833.
4. Ethridge RT, Hashimoto K, Dai HC, Ehlers RA, Rajaraman S and Evers B.M., (2020) Selective inhibition of NF- κ B attenuates the severity of cerulein-induced acute pancreatitis. *J Am Coll Surg.*; 195: 497-505.
5. Prud'homme G.J, Glinka Y, Kurt M, Liu W and Wang Q. (2017) The anti-aging protein Klotho is induced by GABA therapy and exerts protective and stimulatory effects on pancreatic beta cells. *Biochem-Biophys Res Community*; Volume 493: pp. 1542-1547.